

FOODPathS Recommendations

Deliverable 2.8 'Summary of Partnership guidance/mentoring activities presented'

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Summary of Partnership guidance/mentoring activities presented

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VS 3	24/11/2025	EXCOM	Final feedback on Draft
VS 4	28/11/2025	Damien Guimond and Hugo de Vries	Final edits and submission of D2.8

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Executive summary ‘Guidance activities’

The here presented deliverable D2.8 is entitled ‘Summary of Partnership guidance/mentoring activities presented’. This deliverable intends to guide all (forthcoming) partnerships in Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) thanks to a series of recommendations. These recommendations serve as basis of this report, following the statement in the FOODPathS Description of Activities (DoA): ‘*Finally, a summary of guiding activities with lessons learned will be presented to the EC and the SCAR FS SWG in a joint meeting*’.

This joint meeting was the final FOODPathS meeting, held in The Hague, The Netherlands, on the 1st and 2nd of October 2025. At this meeting members from the SCAR, EC, FutureFoodS (the running Partnership on SFS) and Advisory Board (representatives of partnerships and large food system initiatives) were actively present and involved in the formulations of the final versions of the recommendations. Before this final meeting, draft versions of WP-specific recommendations had been prepared by all partners in the work packages (WP). These draft versions had been cross analyzed over the WPs, resulting in 6 key draft recommendations.

Both the 6 key draft recommendations and WP-specific draft recommendations have been discussed in interactive sessions during the final meeting, like in debates, fish bowl and designing sessions. This process and its outcomes are documented below. This allows both taking notice of the final recommendations, but also the process in which they have been defined. We sincerely hope that both the process and outcomes may be of support to anybody involved in (new) partnerships.

Additionally, we have asked single partners representing large networks to provide additional recommendations for partnerships that are relevant for members in their network. A separate chapter is dedicated to these kinds of recommendations.

Finally, we like to underline that the Deliverable D2.7 ‘Manual’ also provides lessons learned and references to all Deliverables with more detailed information.

The final key recommendations are presented below.

- 1. Ensure inclusive, accountable and balanced governance of food system partnerships** by developing shared visions, valuing diverse knowledge systems, embedding long-term engagement, and enforcing transparency and fairness in decision-making and funding.
- 2. Strengthen collaboration in partnerships** by using accessible language, ensuring a transparent modus operandi for operational activities, and creating trusted spaces for dialogues that build understanding and trust among all actors.
- 3. Integrate systems approaches into research and innovation funding** by aligning calls across EU and national levels, introducing diverse and flexible funding schemes, and incentivizing inter- and trans-disciplinarity, multi-actor engagement, and co-creation.
- 4. Build a Community of Practice through a branded network of universities** by adopting a Food Systems Sustainability Charter and concrete commitments, supported by benchmarks, and reinforced with incentives for teaching, research, and practice.
- 5. Establish an independent and inclusive Food Systems Observatory** that synthesizes and translates evidence into policy-relevant advice in interactive manners, ensures transparency, and serves as a global and multi-sectoral **science–policy–society interface**.
- 6. Develop a practical and accessible Knowledge Hub of Food System Labs** that connects existing initiatives via a standardized and comprehensible methodology, links to funding opportunities, employs facilitators, and showcases diverse territorial practices for cross-learning.

Main abbreviations

- CoP:** Community of Practice
- CSA:** Coordinated Support Action
- DoA:** Description of Activities
- DG-RTD:** Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
- EIT (Food):** European Institute of Technology (for Food)
- ETP:** European Technology Platform
- FS:** Food Systems
- FSA:** Food Systems Approach
- FSO:** Food Systems Observatory
- HDHL:** Healthy Diet Healthy Life
- HE:** HorizonEurope (programme)
- HEI:** Higher Education Institutions
- KPI:** Key Performance Indicator
- LL:** Living Lab
- MO:** Modus Operandi
- NFTP:** National Food Technology Platform
- NGO:** Non-Governmental Organization
- PPP:** Public Private Partnerships
- P-SFS:** Partnership on Sustainable Food Systems
- R&D:** Research & Development
- R&I:** Research & Innovation
- RIPE:** Research Innovation Policy Education
- SCAR FS SWG:** Standing Committee on Agricultural Research Food System Strategic Working Group
- SDG:** Sustainable Development Goal
- SFS:** Sustainable Food Systems
- SME:** Small-Medium Enterprise
- SPI:** Science-to-Policy Interface
- SPSI:** Science-to-Policy-to-Society Interface
- SRIA:** Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda
- SSH:** Social Sciences and Humanities

1. Introduction

The FOODPathS project aims to establish a Prototype Partnership for Sustainable Food Systems (SFS). Therefore, it focuses on all essential elements of a partnership, including its governance model, *modus operandi*, co-funding mechanisms, strategic research and innovation agenda with connections to policy and education, best practices of co-creation cases, essential networks and infrastructures, communication strategies, etc (see Figure 1). In other words, FOODPathS tends to design an ideal partnership, thanks to the collective intelligent input of public, private, philanthropic, academic, civil society stakeholders, active at local to global scales.

FOODPathS output is foreseen to guide all (forthcoming) partnerships in SFS thanks to a series of recommendations and the previously published Manual (D2.7). These recommendations form the basis of D2.8 (this report), following the statement in the Description of Activities (DoA; the agreed workplan): ‘*Finally, a summary of guiding activities prepared by INRAE with lessons learned will be presented to the EC and the SCAR FS SWG in a joint meeting*’. Since FutureFoodS, the co-funded Partnership on SFS, already started 1 year after the kick-off of FOODPathS (in its proposal building and execution of its workplan), mentoring has been replaced by involving FutureFoodS representatives in our workshops during the final FOODPathS annual meeting, and in many (joint) workshops before.

Why this deliverable?

The Food System’s Strategic Working Group of the Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR FS SWG) together with the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD) of the European Commission had initiated the development process of the creation of an inclusive Partnership in SFS. A key step in this process was the launch of the FOODPathS project, based on a mini-partnership (see introduction above). After 3.5 years of working on an ideal partnership, the final feedback to and from the SCAR FS SWG and DG RTD will be here presented in the form of guidance recommendations. It may also help both to mentor the activities of running partnerships, in particular FutureFoodS.

A second objective – not written in the DoA – became apparent while running FOODPathS tasks: the partners also would prefer to have a set of recommendations relevant for their represented network of FS actors. This holds at least for those who participate/coordinate in (forthcoming) partnerships, or large initiatives with a diversity of food system actors.

We like to underline that the Deliverable D2.7 ‘Manual’ also provides lessons learned, that can serve anybody involved (or becoming involved) in partnerships.

The structure of this Report

This report is structured as follows:

1. In chapter 2, a set of six key recommendations are shown. These have been formulated on basis of a presentation and discussion of all recommendations elaborated in the work packages. They cover the different elements of the Bird, see Figure 1 below, representing a prototype partnership on sustainable food systems.
2. In the next chapter 3, the major remarks from a debating session at the final FOODPathS meeting in The Hague, 1/10/2025 are presented. Therefore, the 6 key recommendations have been translated into 6 provocative statements that allowed all participants at the meeting to agree or disagree with the statement. All statements have been discussed during 2 hours allowing all participants to express themselves.
3. In the follow-up chapter 4, all recommendations from the 7 work packages (see Figure 2, in chapter 4) are presented; these are based on lessons learned during the 3.5 years of running the FOODPathS project. During the final FOODPathS meeting in The Hague, workshop sessions have been organized to once more reflect on the outputs of these work packages and the formulated deliverables.
4. In the Chapter 5, some single FOODPathS partners representing large networks have provided complementary recommendations with short argumentations.
5. In the final chapter 6, references for further reading are proposed.
6. One Annex provides the workshop agendas during the final FOODPathS meeting in The Hague on the 1st and 2nd of October 2025.

Figure 1 The bird representing the Partnership toward SFS in Europe (Design EUFIC; original source: Modified image from H. Schepers and H. de Vries, <https://hal.inrae.fr/hal-02934667/document>)

2. Six key recommendations

The six final formulated key recommendations are the following:

1. **Ensure inclusive, accountable and balanced governance of food system partnerships** by developing shared visions, valuing diverse knowledge systems, embedding long-term engagement, and enforcing transparency and fairness in decision-making and funding.
2. **Strengthen collaboration in partnerships** by using accessible language, ensuring a transparent modus operandi for operational activities, and creating trusted spaces for dialogues that build understanding and trust among all actors.
3. **Integrate systems approaches into research and innovation funding** by aligning calls across EU and national levels, introducing diverse and flexible funding schemes, and incentivizing inter- and trans-disciplinarity, multi-actor engagement, and co-creation.
4. **Build a Community of Practice through a branded network of universities** by adopting a Food Systems Sustainability Charter and concrete commitments, supported by benchmarks, and reinforced with incentives for teaching, research, and practice.
5. **Establish an independent and inclusive Food Systems Observatory** that synthesizes and translates evidence into policy-relevant advice in interactive manners, ensures transparency, and serves as a global and multi-sectoral **science–policy–society interface**.
6. **Develop a practical and accessible Knowledge Hub of Food System Labs** that connects existing initiatives via a standardized and comprehensible methodology, links to funding opportunities, employs facilitators, and showcases diverse territorial practices for cross-learning.

These have been based on 6 key draft recommendations that were introduced via the following slides and thereafter debated via 6, related, statements during the final FOODPathS meeting in The Hague, 1/10/2025.

Recommendation 1

Ensure an inclusive and balanced governance of food system partnerships by co-creating shared visions, valuing the diversity in knowledge, and guaranteeing fair involvement in decision-making, funding, and opportunities.

Sources:

- <https://zenodo.org/records/15593796> (governance model)
- <https://zenodo.org/records/15586412> (Manual prototype vs 1)
- [10.1007/s43621-024-00648-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-024-00648-x) (governance conceptual framework)
- <https://zenodo.org/records/14588586> (trade-offs and co-benefits)

Source: Deliverable D2.7 FOODPathS (Manual; to be published)

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-024-00648-x>

Recommendation 2

Explain key concepts and boost collaboration opportunities in partnerships by using accessible language, ensuring transparency in operational activities ('Modus Operandi') at all scales, and creating spaces for stakeholders to exchange, learn, and build trust.

Figure 3. The nine key pillars of success for the ideal Partnership.

Concept Tools
Find clear concepts, guidelines and roadmaps you can follow to design and fine-tune your partnership

Mapping Tools
Use practical tools to map cases, best practices and stakeholders to improve your partnerships on different (at local, national, European and international) levels

Engagement Tools
Be inspired by tools to enhance your communication, gather feedback, run impactful events and engage stakeholders, leaving no one behind

Sources:

- <https://zenodo.org/records/15592210> (toolkit; figure above)
- <https://zenodo.org/records/15593669> ('Modus operandi'; figure left)
- <https://zenodo.org/records/15586464> (feedback from society)

Recommendation 3

Integrate systems approaches into research and innovation programming and funding by designing calls with clear definitions, impact frameworks, and incentives for inter-disciplinary, multi-actor and co-creation activities.

Sources:

- <https://zenodo.org/records/15591934> (funding strategies)
- <https://zenodo.org/records/14588685> (funders forum)
- [10.3389/fsufs.2024.1399275](https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2024.1399275) (co-creation)

DOI: [10.3389/fsufs.2024.1399275](https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2024.1399275)

Source: Deliverable D2.7 FOODPaths

Recommendation 4

Build a Community of Practice through a branded network of universities, by adopting a Food Systems Sustainability Charter, developing lifelong-mutual learning programs, skills, micro-credentials, and quality assurance standards.

Sources:

- <https://zenodo.org/records/15593742> (Branded Network)
- <https://zenodo.org/records/14588386> (skills)

Recommendation 5

Establish a Food Systems Observatory and strengthen science-policy-society interfaces to monitor transitions and provide research-based advice, ensure policies are aligned with research and innovation, and build capacity of actors in food systems approaches

(Note that FOODPathS proposed the RIPE concept, linking Research & Innovation (RI) strategies with Policy making (P), and Educate programs (E)).

Sources:

- <https://zenodo.org/records/15591664> (FS approach and Observatory)
- <https://zenodo.org/records/15592057> (SRIA & Science to Policy)
- <https://zenodo.org/records/15591803> (RIPE concepts)
- Deliverable D2.7 FOODPathS (accessible beginning of 2025)

Funded by the European Union

Recommendation 6

Develop a Knowledge Hub of Food System Labs, that shows best FS practices using a single template, employing facilitators and established national platforms, and connecting to communities of practices.

Sources:

- <https://zenodo.org/records/15586528> (Hub of FS Labs)
- <https://zenodo.org/records/15585929> (PPP case studies)
- <https://zenodo.org/records/14587849> (70+ case studies)
- [10.3389/fsufs.2023.1160097](https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2023.1160097) (business models)

Modified from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2022.03.027>

The screenshot shows a table titled 'The seven Food System Hubbing Hubs (like a Guide)'. The table has columns for Food actor, Food value, Hub, Food handling, Hub type, and Hub location. It lists various hubs across different countries.

The screenshot shows the 'Foodtech Living Labs Platform' website. It features a map of Europe with red dots indicating hub locations. To the right is a circular diagram with segments for Policy, Innovation, Research, Education, and Networking, each with a numerical value.

[10.3389/fsufs.2024.1399275](https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2024.1399275)

Funded by the European Union

3. Feedback on the 6 key recommendations from a debating session

Introduction of the debating (feedback) session

Feedback on Draft Recommendations were given by participants during a debating session at the Final FOODPathS meeting, October 1st, 2025. The participants represented the FOODPathS consortium partners, their networks, EC & SCAR SWG FS & FutureFoodS representatives, FOODPathS Advisory Board Members, EU project coordinators, and delegates from the Dutch Agricultural Ministry (hosting the meeting).

The purpose of this meeting was to test the recommendations against the participants’ expertise and experience. Discussions centered on *barriers*, *opportunities*, and *design principles* to further enhance these recommendations as effective and credible. First, the 6 draft recommendations were briefly introduced:

1. Inclusive and balanced governance

Diversity is a strength if governance structures ensure fair representation and accountability. Weak rules, tokenism, and power asymmetries remain the main risks. Inclusiveness must value multiple knowledge systems, not only scientific expertise. Trust requires long-term engagement and co-created visions.

2. Accessible language, transparency, and trust-building

Language differences are real barriers. Terminology must be clear and precise — words like “only” or “labs” can alienate key actors. Transparent operations and structured spaces for dialogue build trust. Accessible language is central to stakeholder engagement and legitimacy.

3. Integrating systems approaches into funding

Short project cycles are misaligned with systemic change. Solutions include modular or relay models, project clusters, and alignment across levels (EU and national). Funding calls should explicitly incentivise interdisciplinarity, co-creation, and multi-actor engagement. Avoiding project ‘fatigue’ is essential to maintain trust.

4. Community of practice and university network

A sustainability charter for universities is both possible and necessary. Precedents in farming show that voluntary charters can build alignment. Diversity of skills is a strength, but credibility depends on concrete commitments. A stepwise process, backed by incentives, is needed to avoid symbolic gestures.

5. Food Systems Observatory and science–policy–society interfaces

Observatories can improve evidence use, but independence and transparency are essential to prevent capture by corporate interests. They must be inclusive, linking stakeholders in co-creation, and broad in scope, covering health and global dimensions. Translation, timing, and dialogue are critical for evidence to influence policy.

6. Knowledge Hub of Food System Labs

The Hub can give visibility to SMEs and connect fragmented initiatives, but should not present itself as the “only” solution. Terminology must be accessible, tools practical, and facilitators active. Linkages to funding opportunities are critical. The Hub should preserve diversity while enabling cross-fertilization.

Then, cross-cutting insights were underlined like:

- **Diversity as an asset:** cooperation thrives when supported by fair rules.
- **Language shapes legitimacy:** precise, clear and inclusive wording is central to trust.
- **Continuity matters:** systemic change needs long-term design and alignment.
- **Credibility through action:** frameworks must go beyond symbolism.
- **Transparency and accountability:** safeguards against undue influence are non-negotiable.
- **Spaces for dialogue:** structured exchanges turn barriers into opportunities.

Then the following statements were presented and debated; participants could agree (green paper) or disagree (red paper). Opposing participants tried to convince each other to change their opinion.

Statement 1. Partnerships fail in being *inclusive & power-balanced* because Food System actors are too different.

Statement 2. The different languages & conflicts of interest of food system actors create a barrier to (multi-actor) cooperation.

Statement 3. The duration of funded projects is too short for exploiting food system approaches.

Statement 4. The large number of needed skills and actions for reaching sustainable food systems excludes agreeing on a common sustainability chart

Statement 5. Policies can be evidence-based, when relying on observatories and exchanges between scientists & policy makers, even in complex food systems

Statement 6. Only a Knowledge Hub of territorial food system labs unite the 'smaller players' (like SME)

Feedback on each recommendation by participants

Recommendation 1 – Inclusive and balanced governance

Draft recommendation 1: **Ensure an inclusive and balanced governance of food system partnerships** by co-creating shared visions, valuing the diversity in knowledge, and guaranteeing fair involvement in decision-making, funding, and opportunities.

Session feedback:

Diversity as a strength, not a weakness

Participants stressed that diversity among actors should not be seen as an obstacle. On the contrary, it can generate richer solutions if managed properly. Differences in perspectives were described as leverage points for innovation when embedded in strong governance frameworks. A participant pointed to the Farm to Fork strategy and Living Labs as illustrations of how diverse perspectives can be harnessed productively. Two observers agreed that inclusiveness depends on governance design and leadership, not on reducing diversity.

The real problem: governance failures and power asymmetries

Many speakers argued that governance failures and power asymmetries are the real obstacles to inclusiveness. A participant emphasized that civil society and farmers often lack the resources to influence discussions compared to large companies. Two other participants explained that unclear rules of participation and dominance by powerful players frequently block cooperation. Another participant proposed multi-level governance models to distribute influence more fairly across scales. She underlined that inclusiveness is often written into design documents but rarely implemented, calling for concrete proof of inclusiveness instead of formal declarations.

Valuing different forms of knowledge

Participants agreed that inclusiveness requires more than representation: it also means recognizing multiple forms of knowledge. One participant argued that scientific, farmer, business and consumer knowledge should all be valued equally. Another added that sectoral "languages" often lead to misunderstandings, and that translators or intermediaries are needed to bridge across domains so that different knowledge systems can be combined.

Barriers as opportunities when managed well

Some participants reframed barriers and conflicts as positive. One participant explained that disagreements can force actors to clarify their positions and negotiate, resulting in stronger compromises. Another echoed this idea in his observer feedback, stressing those effective leaders can transform barriers into opportunities by listening to all perspectives, even uncomfortable ones, and using these to strengthen decisions.

Risks of tokenism and the need for accountability

Concerns were raised about tokenism, where a wide range of actors are invited but have little real influence. Participants suggested safeguards such as rotating roles, quorum rules and transparent agenda-setting. Observers also emphasized the need for accountability mechanisms to enforce inclusiveness. Without them, dominant players will continue to control agendas regardless of formal participation.

Building trust through continuity and shared vision

Trust was identified as a long-term process that requires sustained engagement. One participant warned that when actors feel consulted only temporarily, they disengage. Participants underlined those structures should give stakeholders a long-term stake in partnerships. Co-creating shared visions was seen as essential to anchor inclusiveness in practice and to overcome fragmentation.

Synthesis

Feedback on Recommendation 1 strongly validated its importance. The group agreed that **partnership inclusiveness and balance are not guaranteed by diversity alone**. They depend on:

1. **Governance design** that prevents dominance and ensures fair rules.
2. **Accountability mechanisms** to turn inclusiveness from principle into practice.
3. **Recognition of multiple knowledge systems**, not just scientific expertise.
4. **Leadership and facilitation** that turn barriers into opportunities.
5. **Continuity and co-created visions** to build trust and sustain engagement.

Diversity was broadly framed as a **strength**, but only if embedded in **fair, transparent, and accountable** governance structures that guarantee real influence for all.

Recommendation 2 – Accessible language, transparency, and trust-building in partnerships

Draft recommendation 2: **Explain key concepts and boost collaboration opportunities in partnerships** by using accessible language, ensuring transparency in operational activities (‘Modus Operandi’) at all scales, and creating spaces for stakeholders to exchange, learn, and build trust.

Session feedback:

The challenge of language

Participants agreed that different “languages” used by scientists, policymakers, businesses and NGOs can create real barriers to cooperation. One participant stressed that terms may carry different meanings for

different groups, creating misunderstandings and frustration. Several voices highlighted the need for intermediaries or facilitators who can translate across domains to ensure actors understand one another.

Accessible and inclusive wording

The importance of words themselves came up repeatedly. The phrasing of the statements used in the session, such as the “only” in Statement 2, was decisive in whether participants could agree or not. One participant underlined that precise wording determines whether people can recognize themselves in a collective vision. During the debate on a sustainability charter, confusion between “charter” and “chart” illustrated how a single word can shift the entire discussion. A participant with experience in European partnerships added that drafting language inclusively is slower but more legitimate.

Risks of exclusion through terminology

Concerns were raised that concepts such as “food system labs” may sound too academic or institutional, and that small actors such as SMEs or micro-initiatives may not see themselves reflected in such terminology. Several participants suggested adapting the framing to ensure smaller players can relate to the concepts. Without this, target groups may ignore or misunderstand the structures meant to serve them.

Spaces for exchange and trust-building

Observers and participants noted that collaboration improves when stakeholders have the right spaces to exchange openly. The session’s debate format itself was cited as an example of creating trust and mutual understanding through structured dialogue. One participant stressed the importance of systemic perspectives at city level, describing food governance as a “pilgrimage through departments,” illustrating how deliberate exchange fosters integration.

Transparency in operations

Participants also insisted that operational activities of partnerships and hubs must be transparent. One participant warned that otherwise inclusiveness can remain superficial, with powerful actors still controlling outcomes. Observers reinforced those processes must be clearly explained and accessible, so stakeholders know how decisions are made and how they can contribute.

Synthesis

Together, the feedback confirmed that partnerships will only function inclusively if they use accessible, inclusive language, explain concepts clearly, and provide transparent spaces for exchange and trust-building:

1. **Language differences are real barriers:** sectoral jargon and divergent vocabularies slow down cooperation unless facilitators build bridges across domains.
2. **Terminology risks exclusion:** concepts like “food system labs” may appear too academic, leading SMEs or micro-initiatives not to recognize themselves in these frameworks.
3. **Precise wording shapes consensus:** the phrasing of statements showed how words can decide whether actors align or clash.
4. **Spaces for exchange foster trust:** structured dialogues and deliberative formats allow stakeholders to clarify meanings, build trust, and surface systemic perspectives.
5. **Transparency is essential:** clear procedures and open operations are needed to avoid tokenism and ensure stakeholders know how decisions are made and how they can contribute.

Recommendation 3 – Integrating systems approaches into research and innovation programming and funding

Draft recommendation 3: **Integrate systems approaches into research and innovation programming and funding** by designing calls with clear definitions, impact frameworks, and incentives for inter- and trans-disciplinary, multi-actor and co-creation activities.

Session feedback:

The mismatch between project cycles and systemic change

Participants widely agreed that the short duration of most projects, typically three to four years, is fundamentally misaligned with the long timeframes needed for systemic change in food systems. Two participants acknowledged that the short duration of projects is a genuine limitation, but reminded that budget cycles and accountability frameworks constrain funding rules at both European and national levels. Both underlined the need to design projects so they link together over time rather than working in isolation.

Designing continuity through modular and relay models

Several speakers proposed concrete approaches to embed continuity into project design. One participant described the idea of a “relay” model where one project hands over to the next, avoiding constant reinvention and building cumulative knowledge. Another suggested hybrid designs: a long-term core program complemented by shorter, flexible modules that can adapt to changing contexts. A third reinforced this idea from a management perspective, highlighting the value of project clustering or portfolio approaches, where shorter projects are grouped under a long-term umbrella. These models were seen as a way to integrate systemic approaches into the funding landscape without asking for all projects to become ten years long.

Aligning systemic approaches across funding levels

One participant emphasized that integrating systems approaches is not only about project length but also about alignment across funding streams. He argued that if national funders, HorizonEurope projects, and partnerships like FutureFoodS all work from the same strategic research and innovation agenda, then even shorter projects can contribute to a cumulative systemic impact. Another participant supported this, noting that projects should be designed to feed into larger processes such as partnerships and observatories, creating a structured progression from local pilots to European frameworks.

Building trust and avoiding project fatigue

The human and social dimension of short projects was repeatedly raised. One participant explained that civil society and communities often experience “project fatigue” — they are engaged for a short period and then abandoned when funding ends. This damages trust and makes actors less willing to collaborate in future initiatives. Two participants added that in cities, short pilots often produce “orphan initiatives” that disappear when funding ends, frustrating local administrations and undermining credibility. Participants argued that embedding continuity and sustainability requirements into project design is essential to maintain trust and legitimacy.

Incentivizing interdisciplinarity and co-creation

Several participants stressed that a systems approach requires interdisciplinarity and multi-actor engagement. Calls for proposals must explicitly encourage this through clear definitions, impact frameworks, and incentives. Without these, consortia tend to remain disciplinary and narrowly focused, delivering fragmented outcomes

rather than systemic solutions. Participants agreed that funding mechanisms should be explicit in demanding co-creation and collaboration across disciplines and sectors.

Synthesis

Feedback strongly confirmed the need to align project funding and design with systemic approaches:

1. **Short projects are misaligned with systemic change:** food system transformation requires long-term perspectives that cannot be captured in three years.
2. **Continuity must be designed in:** modular, relay, and clustered models can ensure knowledge accumulates across projects and avoids fragmentation.
3. **Alignment across levels multiplies impact:** national, European, and partnership calls should follow shared agendas to ensure shorter projects contribute to systemic outcomes.
4. **Trust and legitimacy are at stake:** project fatigue in communities and cities erodes credibility, so continuity mechanisms and embedding in governance are essential.
5. **Systems approaches need incentives:** calls must clearly demand interdisciplinarity, multi-actor engagement, and co-creation, or else projects risk falling back into silos.

Recommendation 4 – Community of practice and a branded university network

Draft recommendation 4: **Build a Community of Practice through a branded network of universities**, by adopting a Food Systems Sustainability Charter, developing lifelong-mutual learning programs, skills, micro-credentials, and quality assurance standards.

Session feedback:

The case for a sustainability charter

Many participants strongly rejected the idea that the large number of skills and actions required for food system transformation excludes the possibility of a common charter. On the contrary, they argued that a sustainability charter is both feasible and necessary to give coherence to a branded university network. Without it, universities risk fragmenting their sustainability efforts and losing visibility. A charter was seen as a way to provide a clear, common reference point that would unify diverse institutions around shared principles. One participant stressed that such a framework would give universities legitimacy in the eyes of students, funders and society. Another participant supported this line, noting that many global organizations and universities already sign sustainability charters; this demonstrates that it is not only possible, but also desirable, for a food systems charter to exist.

Precedents from farming and sectoral networks

Participants highlighted those charters and codes of practice are not new in Europe’s food and agriculture sectors. One participant explained that farmers’ organizations and professional associations already rely on such frameworks to build credibility, align diverse interests, and demonstrate shared commitments despite very different production systems. These precedents were presented as evidence that voluntary agreements are possible even in contexts with highly diverse actors, and that they can generate trust among stakeholders. The farming example is an illustration that a food systems charter for universities is not an unrealistic ambition but a continuation of practices that already exist and deliver value in other parts of the food chain.

Diversity as a strength rather than an obstacle

Participants disagreed with the framing that too many skills make agreement impossible. Instead, they underlined that diversity should be celebrated as a defining strength of a sustainability charter. One participant argued that interdisciplinarity and multi-actor engagement are precisely what a food system–focused charter should highlight. Another reinforced this perspective by saying that the breadth of expertise involved in food systems is not a problem to be pushed away, but a richness that a charter can bring together. By explicitly valuing different skills and domains, a charter would demonstrate that systemic change depends on multiple disciplines and actors working side by side.

Risks of tokenism and symbolic charters

Despite this general support, several voices cautioned that a charter carries risks if not designed carefully. Two participants warned that if the document is too generic, it will become a symbolic gesture that everyone can sign without making real changes. For them, a charter only has meaning if it leads to tangible commitments such as changes in teaching, research priorities, campus practices, and external partnerships. A “lowest common denominator” charter would risk undermining credibility rather than enhancing it. Participants therefore stressed that credibility is built not through words alone, but through evidence that universities live up to the commitments they endorse.

Stepwise approaches and the importance of incentives

Linked to these cautions, a number of participants proposed a stepwise or phased approach. One participant suggested starting with mapping and benchmarking existing practices across universities, using these experiences to develop a body of evidence about what sustainability in food systems looks like in practice. From there, a charter could be consolidated on the basis of concrete achievements rather than abstract declarations. Another added that universities already sign onto other international sustainability frameworks, and that food systems–specific commitments could grow from those existing efforts. However, she underlined those incentives would be crucial: without tangible benefits for members, universities may see little value in going beyond symbolic participation. A branded network must therefore combine the reputational benefits of a charter with practical advantages such as access to resources, recognition, or enhanced collaboration opportunities.

Synthesis

Feedback on Recommendation 4 showed broad support for the idea of a branded university network anchored in a sustainability charter, but also clear warnings on how it should be designed and implemented:

1. **A charter is both possible and necessary** to give coherence, credibility and external legitimacy to universities’ sustainability commitments.
2. **Precedents in farming and sectoral networks** show that voluntary charters and codes of practice already work as tools to build trust and alignment among diverse actors.
3. **The diversity of skills and domains** required is not an obstacle, but a richness that the charter should explicitly highlight as a core strength.
4. **The risk lies in creating a charter that is too generic**; credibility requires concrete commitments that change practice, not only signatures.
5. **A stepwise process should be followed**: start with mapping practices and building benchmarks, then consolidate into a formal charter backed by lived experience.
6. **Incentives and practical benefits are essential** so that universities have real motivation to join and live up to their commitments.

Recommendation 5 – Food Systems Observatory and science–policy–society interfaces

Draft recommendation 5: **Establish a Food Systems Observatory and strengthen science-policy-society interfaces** to monitor transitions and provide research-based advice, ensure policies are aligned with research and innovation, and build capacity of actors in food systems approaches (note that FOODPathS proposed the RIPE concept, linking Research & Innovation (RI) strategies with Policy making (P), and Educate programs (E)).

Session feedback:

The role of observatories in evidence-based policy

Participants widely agreed that observatories can be powerful tools to ground policymaking in real evidence. One participant argued that in complex food systems, decision-makers often face information overload and conflicting narratives. Observatories can help by synthesizing and translating evidence into usable forms. For her, the value of observatories lies in making information **digestible and actionable**, rather than overwhelming. This view resonated with many others, who stressed that the central promise of observatories is to make evidence more accessible and timelier for policymakers.

Evidence, values, and politics

Despite this recognition, several participants cautioned that policies are never based on evidence alone. One participant underlined those decisions always blend evidence with political priorities, stakeholder values, and power dynamics. Another participant expanded on this, noting that even robust data can be interpreted differently by different actors, especially in contested fields such as food systems. Observatories should therefore not be expected to “depoliticize” policymaking. Instead, they should be seen as **support tools** that strengthen the use of evidence while recognizing that values and politics inevitably play a role.

Safeguards for independence and trust

A strong warning came from one participant, who explained how some large companies manipulate evidence by financing or producing pseudo-scientific studies that appear neutral but are designed to defend their interests. She insisted that observatories must have **safeguards for independence and transparency**, otherwise they risk being captured by powerful actors and losing legitimacy. Several other participants agreed that credibility depends on the integrity of evidence, and that trust cannot be built if observatories are seen as biased or dominated by particular interests.

Inclusiveness and participation

One participant argued that observatories must not be closed expert spaces. Too often they are dominated by scientists and technical specialists, leaving out industry, practitioners, or civil society. Another participant reinforced this, advocating a **co-creation model** where stakeholders are involved from the start in defining what should be monitored and how evidence is to be used. Inclusiveness was described as essential for ensuring observatories are trusted and relevant. Otherwise, they risk being dismissed as elitist and disconnected from real food system dynamics.

The need for translation and mediation

Several contributions focused on the gap between scientific outputs and policy needs. One participant stressed that scientific studies are often too technical or fragmented. Policymakers, in contrast, require clear narratives, actionable insights, and information delivered in line with political cycles. Another participant added that timing and framing are decisive: even robust evidence is ignored if it arrives too late or is not communicated in a way

policymakers can use. He called for stronger **science–policy interfaces** to contextualize and translate data into actionable policy advice.

Scope and relevance of observatories

Participants also discussed the scope of observatories. One participant argued that food systems are global, and observatories must therefore link across scales. He warned against a narrow EU-only perspective, pointing to climate and biodiversity challenges that transcend borders. Another participant added that observatories must not limit themselves to agricultural or production data: nutrition and public health outcomes are equally important dimensions if policies are to be genuinely evidence-based. For both, the key was to ensure observatories reflect the **full breadth of food system challenges**.

Observatories as spaces for dialogue

Finally, one participant suggested that observatories should not be seen only as data repositories, but also as **facilitators of dialogue**. By bringing different stakeholders around the same evidence, they can create spaces where scientific findings are confronted with values, trade-offs and experiences. This dialogical role was seen as critical for embedding observatories in systemic approaches, ensuring they go beyond monitoring to enable collective sense-making.

Synthesis

Feedback on Recommendation 5 showed broad support but also clear conditions for success:

1. **Observatories can strengthen evidence use** by synthesizing and translating complex information into usable advice for policymakers.
2. **Evidence is never enough on its own**: observatories should be seen as support tools in a political process that always blends values and interests.
3. **Independence and transparency are essential** to protect against manipulation and ensure credibility.
4. **Inclusiveness and co-creation are required** so observatories are trusted and relevant to all actors, not only experts.
5. **Translation and timing are decisive**: evidence must be delivered in clear, actionable formats aligned with policy cycles.
6. **The scope of observatories must be broad**, covering global dimensions and including nutrition and health alongside production and economic data.
7. **Observatories should facilitate dialogue**, enabling evidence to be confronted with values and trade-offs, and supporting systemic governance.

Recommendation 6 – Knowledge Hub of Food System Labs

Draft recommendation 6: **Develop a Knowledge Hub of Food System Labs**, that shows best FS practices using a single template, employing facilitators and established national platforms, and connecting to communities of practices.

Session feedback:

The potential of a Knowledge Hub

Participants acknowledged the value of a Knowledge Hub to connect smaller actors such as SMEs, labs, and local initiatives that often feel isolated. One participant argued that a Hub could give visibility and collective

voice to these actors, allowing them to share practices and connect to broader innovation processes. Another participant, speaking from the aquaculture perspective, confirmed that SMEs frequently lack avenues to be heard at the European level. A Hub that is practical and focused on best practices could provide a **living resource** for connecting fragmented initiatives and avoiding duplication.

Concerns about exclusivity

A major issue raised was the framing of the Hub as the “only” solution for uniting smaller players. One participant challenged this wording, stressing that SMEs need multiple channels for collaboration and that existing clusters, platforms, and networks should be linked rather than replaced. Another participant added that language matters: portraying the Hub as the single solution risks alienating actors who are already active in other networks. The feedback highlighted that a Hub should be positioned as a **connector and amplifier**, not as a monopoly structure.

Risks of exclusion through terminology

Participants underlined that the concept of “food system labs” may sound academic and abstract to SMEs or community initiatives. There was a risk that smaller actors would not recognize themselves in the concept, leading to low engagement. Several voices suggested adapting the vocabulary and framing so that it resonates with those on the ground. Without inclusive and clear language, the Hub might be dismissed as an expert-driven tool irrelevant to real practitioners.

Practical accessibility and usability

Concerns were voiced that a Knowledge Hub could become “just another website” unless it offers practical value. Participants stressed the need for a **user-friendly design** with clear tools, matchmaking functions, and easy navigation. Facilitators should play a role in guiding actors, translating information, and ensuring that the Hub is not limited to static documents. National platforms were suggested as anchors for this work, ensuring local accessibility and uptake.

Connection to funding and real incentives

A recurring point was that without a link to funding streams, the Hub risks being symbolic. Several participants argued that the Hub should not only collect knowledge but also help SMEs and labs connect to funding opportunities or calls. Practical examples of how to apply for support or align with European programs would give the Hub real added value.

The importance of diversity and context

Participants also warned against homogenization. Food system transformation is context-dependent, and local solutions cannot always be generalized. A European-level Hub must therefore allow diversity while promoting cross-fertilization. Instead of trying to unite everything into one model, it should showcase the variety of territorial approaches and provide tools to compare and learn from them.

Synthesis

Feedback on Recommendation 6 confirmed that a Knowledge Hub could be a valuable tool, but only under certain conditions:

1. **The Hub should connect and amplify existing initiatives**, not present itself as the only solution.
2. **Terminology matters**: concepts like “food system labs” must be reframed in accessible language that resonates with SMEs and local actors.
3. **Practical value is essential**: the Hub must provide usable tools, matchmaking functions, and facilitation, not just a static repository.

4. **Linkages to funding opportunities are critical**, giving SMEs incentives to engage and ensuring the Hub drives real action.
5. **Diversity must be preserved**: the Hub should respect local contexts while enabling cross-fertilization and exchange across regions.

Synthesis and Conclusion

The discussions around the six draft recommendations confirmed their **overall relevance and value for shaping future food systems partnerships**. Across all debates, participants recognized the importance of inclusive governance, clear and accessible language, systemic approaches in research and innovation, and the need for tools such as charters, observatories, and hubs to provide coherence and continuity.

At the same time, the feedback revealed **recurring risks**: tokenism, power imbalances, project fatigue, symbolic commitments, and the capture of evidence by dominant interests.

Several **cross-cutting insights** emerged, which could address those risks. First, **diversity must be understood as a resource (or enabler) rather than a barrier**. The richness of perspectives across sectors, disciplines and communities can strengthen outcomes, provided governance frameworks guarantee fairness and transparency. Second, **language is not neutral**: wording, terminology, and the clarity of concepts fundamentally shape whether actors feel included or excluded. The success of future partnerships will depend on how concepts are framed and communicated. Third, **continuity is crucial**. Systemic transformation requires long-term perspectives, but current project and funding cycles are too short. Relay models, modular designs and alignment across national and EU levels are essential to avoid fragmentation and project fatigue.

A further insight is the importance of **credibility through action**. Participants repeatedly warned that frameworks such as charters, observatories or hubs risk being symbolic unless they generate tangible commitments, measurable outcomes, and visible benefits for stakeholders. Safeguards against capture, independence of evidence, and robust accountability mechanisms are indispensable for ensuring trust. Finally, the debate itself showed the value of **structured spaces for dialogue**. By debating provocative statements, participants engaged openly with tensions and contradictions, turning barriers into opportunities for learning and trust-building.

In conclusion, the feedback provides a strong validation and mandate for refining the six recommendations. Each of them was validated but also sharpened by the concerns raised. The path forward should be to:

- i. Translate recommendations into **practical designs** that ensure inclusiveness, continuity, and accountability.
- ii. Test frameworks (charters, hubs, observatories) through **phased approaches**, starting with pilot practices before scaling up.
- iii. Ensure **coherence across levels**, linking EU initiatives, national platforms, and local actors in a way that respects diversity while promoting cross-fertilization.
- iv. Invest in **leadership and facilitation capacity**, recognizing that trust and dialogue are as important as technical tools.

By integrating these lessons, FOODPathS and its partners moved to the formulation of the final recommendations. Based on the FOODPathS legacy, the next recommended step is to define actionable strategies that support lasting and legitimate food system transformation.

Proposed updated recommendations (see also previous chapter: the text block)

1. **Ensure inclusive, accountable and balanced governance of food system partnerships** by developing shared visions, valuing diverse knowledge systems, embedding long-term engagement, and enforcing transparency and fairness in decision-making and funding.
2. **Strengthen collaboration in partnerships** by using accessible language, ensuring a transparent modus operandi for operational activities, and creating trusted spaces for dialogues that build understanding and trust among all actors.
3. **Integrate systems approaches into research and innovation funding** by aligning calls across EU and national levels, introducing diverse and flexible funding schemes, and incentivizing inter- and trans-disciplinarity, multi-actor engagement, and co-creation.
4. **Build a Community of Practice through a branded network of universities** by adopting a Food Systems Sustainability Charter and concrete commitments, supported by benchmarks, and reinforced with incentives for teaching, research, and practice.
5. **Establish an independent and inclusive Food Systems Observatory** that synthesizes and translates evidence into policy-relevant advice in interactive manners, ensures transparency, and serves as a global and multi-sectoral **science–policy–society interface**.
6. **Develop a practical and accessible Knowledge Hub of Food System Labs** that connects existing initiatives via a standardized and comprehensible methodology, links to funding opportunities, employs facilitators, and showcases diverse territorial practices for cross-learning.

4. Individual recommendations from each work package and reflections from workshop sessions during the 2025 Annual Meeting

Recommendations per Work Package have been formulated after 3.5 years of working in each WP. The names of the work packages are provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The 8 work packages in FOODPathS

For each WP, the following series of recommendations are given below.

From WP3 'Co-funding'

WP3 specific recommendations are:

- 1) **Integration of a Food Systems Approach (FSA) into R&I programming and funding cycles** still needs stronger efforts – in fact FSA is not enough, we need also **transformative knowledge**.
- 2) **Funding activities**, such as calls, need to be **designed in light of an FSA** from the very beginning; this means clear terminology, definitions, a guiding structure (impact framework) and relevant criteria (see call analysis and recommendations; see focus groups recommendations).
- 3) The following elements are of major importance but need **more emphasis**, and need to be backed up with **incentives**:
 - **Stakeholder engagement, multi-actor-approach**

- **Cross-disciplinarity, especially trans-disciplinarity**
 - **Co-creation, e.g.**, in design of programmes, calls, projects, training for skills, for power relations and decision-making, equity, inclusiveness, and meaningful inclusion.
- 4) Joint involvement and **co-creation of different actors** in R&I funding programmes is important but needs sufficient resources, time and space for building trust, relationships and a common understanding in order to work towards aligned goals and impact („what means impact to you?“), e.g.:
 - Collaboration of funders from different sectors, or geographies
 - Researchers from different disciplines
 - Various stakeholders
 - Different PS or programmes
 - 5) For funding programs to enable impactful R&I following a FSA, **a long-term** planning of the programming and funding cycle is recommended, which means integration of **feedback and learning mechanisms and flexibility to adapt**.
 - 6) Work with „angels/ intermediates/ brokers/ facilitators“, and also „knowledge hubs/ satellites“ to **connect better** and more effectively.
 - 7) Invest in **capacities of people** (funders, researchers, managers, evaluators) on FSA, ToC etc. and better valorize the potential of **mutual learning and collective power** (networks and portfolios!).

Feedback from final meeting workshop session: Inclusive Science-to-Policy Dialogue

“Opening the black box of science-to-policy – making it inclusive and meaningful”

Introduction

The session took place during the **final meeting of the FOODPathS project** in The Hague, as part of the consortium’s collective reflection on the outcomes and lessons of the project. This session specifically addresses issues relevant in both WP3 and WP6, hence, they are not repeated in WP6.

The project’s final meeting brought together partners, associated networks, and representatives from European and national administrations, funders, and stakeholder organizations. This fishbowl session on Day 2 was designed to distil practical insights from the project’s work on science-policy interfaces (SPI/SPSI) and on the Food Systems Approach (FSA) in research and innovation (R&I) programming. It served as a bridge between FOODPathS’ analytical outputs – particularly the recommendations for SPI/SPSI developed in WP6 and the funding-cycle analyses in WP3 – and the perspectives of practitioners who shape and use research-based advice. The session combined invited panelists from ministries, EU initiatives, and research networks with open audience participation, allowing a rotating discussion on three guiding questions in each of its two parts.

- **Part I** addressed *research-based advice to policy makers in a Food Systems Approach*. Its three guiding questions examined (1) how scientific advice is used and transmitted to policy makers, (2) what challenges are encountered in providing and using such advice, and (3) how inclusive and trustworthy SPI/SPSI mechanisms can be organized.
- **Part II** turned the perspective toward the *R&I funding cycle*, asking (1) where in the cycle policy needs can most effectively connect to programming, (2) how to design funding mechanisms that deliver policy relevance, and (3) how to strengthen policy interfaces within funded projects.

The session’s goals were twofold:

1. To test and enrich the FOODPathS recommendations on SPI/SPSI and R&I alignment with feedback from experienced actors at European, national, and regional levels.
2. To assess, through concrete discussion, whether the project’s proposed practices – co-creation, cross-sectoral governance, and multi-actor engagement – resonate with those who will operate the future Sustainable Food Systems Partnership and their funding programs.

Across both parts, the conversation demonstrated that the session's objectives were largely achieved. Participants confirmed that the key issues identified by FOODPathS – fragmented advisory processes, the need for timing and trust between science and policy, and the challenge of embedding policy relevance in R&I systems – accurately reflect the field's realities. The debate also produced converging views on practical pathways forward. Taken together, the discussions validated the project's analytical findings and the way they have been transformed into shared operational recommendations. They illustrated that the vision of FOODPathS – a self-organising, inclusive, and learning-based partnership model – is both realistic and widely supported among the policy and research communities that will shape its implementation.

Synthesis of session outputs and feedback to FOODPathS

The following synthesis summarizes the main insights emerging from the two-part fishbowl session held during the final meeting of the FOODPathS project in The Hague. It distils the reflections and feedback of participants without reproducing the detailed transcript. The session brought together a diverse group of actors involved in the science–policy and research–funding landscape: representatives of European and national administrations, research organizations, funding agencies, stakeholder platforms, and regional innovation networks. Several were active in related initiatives such as the SCAR Working Group on Food Systems, HDHL, BIOEAST, and ERIAFF, providing complementary views from the policy, research, and implementation sides of the food-system transition.

Validation of FOODPathS findings

Across interventions, participants confirmed that the key issues analyzed by FOODPathS reflect their own experience: Diversity and lack of shared principles and practices in research-based advisory processes, weak coordination across sectors, and the difficulty of aligning research timelines with policy decision cycles. They recognized that the Food Systems Approach (FSA) inherently multiplies interfaces between policy areas – agriculture, health, environment, and economy – and that the challenge now is to turn this complexity into coherence.

The discussions therefore validated FOODPathS' analytical diagnosis while moving it from conceptual framing toward practical implementation pathways for research programming and the future Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the Sustainable Food Systems Partnership.

Science–policy interfaces: conditions for effective advice (Part I)

Participants presented a diverse understanding of how scientific evidence reaches - and should reach - decision makers either directly or through **knowledge intermediaries** – agencies, research councils, and cross-sectoral platforms, which may play a role in translating and contextualizing results. The effectiveness of these interfaces depends primarily on transparent processes based on principles for quality assurance and integrity which again should ensure **timing and trust (Science policy Interfaces, SPI)**. Moreover, research-based evidence must coincide with policy windows and be supported by processes perceived as credible. Participants - including those representing stakeholder interests - agreed that innovative processes for SPI should be developed, which allows for co-creation and engagement of input from wider knowledge systems and stakeholders, so-called Science Policy Society Interfaces (SPSI).

While several participants supported the establishment of more formal coordination mechanisms to ensure policy coherence and scientific integrity, others emphasized the value of **informal and flexible exchanges** based on personal relationships. All concurred that inclusiveness and integrity can coexist when transparency is assured.

Examples from European agencies, national institutes, and city networks illustrated a growing interest in **co-creation formats** for SPSI such as joint trainings, participatory foresight exercises, and stakeholder dialogues. These mechanisms were seen as key enablers for operationalizing the SRIA and ensuring that its priorities remain grounded in societal needs.

Policy needs and the R&I funding cycle (Part II, Question 1–2)

The second part of the session turned to how **policy priorities can influence R&I programming** and how funding mechanisms can deliver policy relevance. Participants converged on several messages:

- Policy relevance must be **embedded right from the start**, particularly at the agenda-setting and call-design stages of the funding cycle.

- **Coordination across ministries and agencies** is essential to address food systems as cross-cutting missions rather than isolated sectors.
- **Continuity across research phases** – from proof of concept to pilot implementation and policy uptake – should be ensured through multi-stage or follow-up funding instruments.
- Investment in **shared knowledge platforms and repositories** is needed to maintain institutional memory and allow evidence from successive programmes to accumulate and remain accessible.
- **Inclusiveness** was identified as a prerequisite for legitimacy: smaller Member States, regional authorities, and local actors must be able to contribute to defining research needs and shaping future funding calls. Regional networks (e.g. ERIAFF) and transnational initiatives (HDHL, BIOEAST) were cited as working examples of multi-level coordination that could inspire the operational framework of the future Partnership.

Strengthening the policy interface within projects (Part II, Question 3)

Participants emphasized that individual research projects should themselves function as **operational science–policy interfaces**. To achieve this, projects should:

- establish **advisory or mirror groups** involving policy representatives;
- prepare explicit **policy-engagement plans** alongside data-management and ethics plans;
- dedicate resources to **professional communication and knowledge brokerage**;
- cluster related projects to produce **synthesized policy briefs**; and
- organize mid-term dialogues with administrations to interpret findings before final reporting. These practices were viewed as essential to enhance the **uptake of project results** and to ensure that the SRIA is continuously informed by evidence emerging from ongoing research.

Cross-cutting messages

The debate produced a coherent set of cross-cutting messages that reinforce the orientation of FOODPathS toward a learning, adaptive Partnership:

1. **Continuity**: sustained interaction across the policy–research–innovation cycle, preventing knowledge loss between projects and programmes.
2. **Coherence**: alignment across ministries, sectors, and governance levels to integrate food-system objectives in a single policy narrative. Ensuring the integration of knowledge gaps identified via SPI processes into R&I programming to support future research-based policy advice.
3. **Co-creation**: systematic engagement of stakeholders and funders in defining, implementing, and evaluating food systems transformation research priorities under transparent rules.

Together, these principles outline the practical conditions under which the future **Sustainable Food Systems Partnership** can implement its SRIA effectively, linking science, innovation, and policy for tangible societal impact.

These collective insights provided concrete, actionable feedback to the FOODPathS team and its partners. They demonstrate that the project’s analyses and recommendations are perceived as timely and relevant for the next stage – translating the Partnership’s vision and SRIA into coordinated funding actions and enduring science-policy interfaces.

Conclusion

The fishbowl session confirmed that the themes addressed by FOODPathS – science-policy interaction, the alignment of research with policy cycles, and the implementation of a Food Systems Approach in R&I – are central to the success of a Sustainable Food Systems Partnership. Participants’ feedback validated the project’s analyses and transformed its conceptual propositions into actionable orientations.

Across both parts of the discussion, there was a clear movement **from diagnosis to delivery**. The exchanges moved beyond identifying obstacles to proposing concrete pathways for implementation: stronger and more transparent interfaces between science and policy; coordination across ministries and funding bodies;

mechanisms to ensure continuity from research to policy uptake; and the embedding of policy engagement directly within projects. These contributions showed that the community of potential Partnership actors already shares a **common vocabulary and purpose** for putting the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda into practice.

The session also underscored the importance of **mutual learning and adaptability**. Whether through formal platforms or flexible collaborations, participants highlighted the need for systems that evolve with experience and remain open to a diversity of knowledge sources. This collective commitment to learning is what will sustain the long-term relevance of the Partnership.

In summary, the discussion achieved its objectives: it validated FOODPathS’ conclusions, produced new insights to guide the implementation of the SRIA, and demonstrated that the model of a **self-organizing, inclusive, and policy-responsive Partnership** is both feasible and supported by a broad spectrum of stakeholders. The outcomes of this exchange could now serve as a reference point for the transition from the prototype developed in FOODPathS to an operational Partnership under Horizon Europe.

From WP4 ‘Food System Labs’

WP4 specific recommendations are:

1. **Reinvest in and formalize NFTP as national intermediaries.** Empower NFTPs to bridge local/regional actors and SMEs with EU frameworks, connect research–industry–policy, and channel national insights into EU agendas.
2. **Mainstream the Pact for Skills across food-system policies and programmes.** Build skills, intelligence and clear up/re-skilling pathways (incl. micro-credentials and peer learning) tailored to SMEs, farmers and industry, co-designed with private partners.
3. **Leverage Food for Life national platforms as the reference PPP model.** Use proven technical-platform structures (e.g., CL.A.N., CTPP, PTF4LS) to drive co-creation, joint working groups, and replication of successful practices across countries.
4. **Strengthen capacity building and attract young talent through the Pact for Skills.** Align training and career pathways (apprenticeships, micro-credentials, mentorship) to upskill the workforce and make the agri-food sector more attractive for young professionals.

Feedback from final meeting session: Open space workshop on the Knowledge-Hub (Living Labs)

Additionally, the recommendations have been discussed at the Workshop on 2/10/2025 (The Hague, Final FOODPathS Project meeting). The main feedback is summarized for the design and the governance as follows:

- A. Regarding design and functionality of the Knowledge Hub
 - Create a common digital space for sharing knowledge, data, agendas, and collaborative strategies.
 - Provide practical and curated resources: case studies, policy briefs, infographics, videos, etc.
 - Focus on targeted and user-friendly functionalities, prioritizing services such as matchmaking and networking opportunities.
 - Ensure the Hub is interactive and dynamic, not just a repository, promote live events, physical gatherings, and community exchange.
- B. Regarding Governance, participation, and inclusivity of the Knowledge Hub of FS Labs
 - Build a co-management governance model with equal partner/member involvement.
 - Develop a participatory structure that allows members to shape content and invite others.
 - Guarantee diverse stakeholder inclusion: SMEs, farmers, city networks, researchers, policy-makers, and civil society.
 - Involve Living Labs as territorial nodes, ensuring bottom-up contributions and feedback.
 - Promote balanced representation across geographic, thematic, and sectoral dimensions.

In more detail, the following remarks are worth considering, responding to three main questions:

1. What are the top 2–3 functionalities or services the Knowledge Hub should prioritise in its first phase to be useful?

- Create a **common space** for actors to share knowledge, data, agendas and strategies to implement together.
- The Hub should act as a **connecting point between local, national, and EU levels**, supporting dialogue to co-design a shared framework.
- **Idea-sharing** should be central: collect expectations on food systems and enable mutual learning.
- Avoid “just another online community” – instead, **focus on essentials and in-person gatherings**.
- Provide **practical resources and communication tools**: case studies, policy briefs, infographics, videos, etc.
- Use the Hub to **translate research into policy design**, inspired by successful national examples (like in The Netherlands).
- Offer **matching opportunities** for organizations – showing how clear value can motivate commitment (e.g. members willing to pay a fee).
- Ensure a **targeted stakeholder engagement strategy** to make the Hub attractive and accessible to all users.
- The Hub should be **digital but built for long-term continuity**, with user-friendly dissemination and interaction.

2. What governance and funding model would make the Hub sustainable and inclusive?

- The Hub should be **co-managed by its partners and members**, with equal engagement in ensuring its efficiency.
- Build a **clear and participatory governance model**, allowing members to invite others and engage in shaping the Hub.
- Involve **diverse actors** – not just researchers, but also businesses, cities, farmers, and other stakeholders.
- There are **too many existing projects and knowledge hubs**; it's essential to define a shared narrative and focus on priority topics.
- **Local Living Labs** can serve as nodes to collect and feedback contributions to the system.
- **Maintaining diversity** in food systems must remain a core driver, avoiding over-standardization.

3. What concrete next steps are needed to move from concept to implementation?

- Identify **clear topics and specific target groups** to include in the scope, enabling meaningful and accessible exchanges.
- Create a **dedicated space to discuss how to build and apply knowledge** from local initiatives, how to scale them, and how to build a strong narrative.
- Develop a **strategy to align stakeholder interests**, avoiding the “noise” from too many disconnected projects.
- Focus on **concrete and impactful actions**, especially at the local level, that bring real value to participants.
- Establish **monitoring and tracking mechanisms** to assess how helpful and effective the Hub is over time.
- A similar model has already existed in various forms – the key challenge is to **realistically integrate all stakeholders**, beyond the research community.

From WP5 'Branded network of universities'

WP5 specific recommendations are:

Regarding the European network for food sustainability education

1. The network can be developed into a Community of Practice (CoP) through the establishment of a clear governance structure, drawing on examples from partners with proven concepts for sustainable food systems education, with the sustainability charter serving as a binding factor and guidance.
2. Strategic priorities include the dissemination of exemplary practices from leading universities, supporting the integration of food system institutes within each institution. Further opportunities lie in advancing lifelong learning pathways and developing micro-credentials within the network.
3. The Community of Practice may be established through the current Partnership call or alternatively through other EU funding instruments, such as Erasmus+.

Regarding the Food Systems sustainability charter

4. The sustainability charter should be adopted in tandem with the establishment of the Community of Practice, while being further co-created with members of the community and sustainable food system stakeholders. The accompanying Code of Conduct should remain flexible and adaptable to the specific context of each university.
5. As there is currently no quality assurance scheme for food systems, such a framework can be developed within the network, drawing on activities across education, campus operations, and related initiatives, and co-designed with food system actors, educators, and students. In this process, collaboration with established organizations such as EASPA and ECA can provide valuable expertise and recognition.
6. Further investigate the possibility of a portfolio of courses and joint degrees with support of ECA for accreditation.
7. Further research on administrative and legislative barriers while promoting inclusivity for diverse institutions.
8. Clearly identify the Community, the domain and the practices; you need to clearly define what the CoP will give to the community and what the Community gives to the CoP, and also what will be the channels to be used by the CoP.

Regarding next steps after FOODPathS

9. The project should progress from concept to practice by implementing each partnership element within the broader ecosystem through pilots, testing, and stakeholder collaboration.
10. To ensure active participation, stakeholders in FOODPathS should be offered both binding incentives and clear short- and long-term benefits, for example calls for pilot, access to funding, etc.
11. A follow-up project could create a base for collaboration between the different partnerships in the Food System; modify the manual in such a way that the 7 bird components fit all partnerships. Respond to questions like: What are the common grounds between partnerships? Where do they show similarities? What are the challenges to support innovations? What are the actions in a single partnership that may impact the other Partnerships? How do the actions of a single partnership influence the Food system? How do other actions influence the Food System?
12. There are certain elements of the Bird that didn't reach their full development (for example the link between Education and R&I and Policies); these could be further developed.
13. Increase the role of technology and of data sharing as an additional component of the manual. Currently the data sharing in the food system is mainly either in the Agri-sector, or at the end of the food (at the consumer level).
14. Potential follow-up actions could be:

- a. Managing the Community of Practice and stakeholder engagement for the CoP with Young EFFoST.
- b. Co-develop the framework of the Community of Practice and ensure implementation of sustainability charter.
- c. Integration of the CoP into larger ecosystem of FOODPathS partnerships.

Feedback from final meeting session: Open space workshop on Community of Practice and university networks

Community of Practice (Living labs and university networks) - What do we need to work on and how do we work on this?

Potential benefits of an SFS Education CoP

Participants agreed that a CoP could serve as a valuable platform for connecting educational institutions working towards more sustainable food systems. It was viewed as a way to exchange best practices, align curricula, and strengthen the role of education in driving the food system transition. However, some participants cautioned that a CoP focused solely on universities might be too narrow in scope. To achieve impact across the entire education system, it should also involve other stakeholders such as vocational schools, teacher networks, students, and non-academic actors.

Expectations and contributions

Participants expected the CoP to provide guidance, tools, and a common framework for integrating sustainability across education. They also expressed willingness to share their institutional experiences and pilot initiatives, particularly in curriculum innovation and university collaboration.

The CoP could facilitate peer learning, case exchange, and joint initiatives, especially by learning from regional best practices, with Seinäjoki University of Applied Sciences (SeAMK) cited as an example of systemic collaboration between universities, government, and education stakeholders.

Governance principles

Participants questioned who would be responsible for governing and maintaining the CoP, underlining the need for a clear structure to ensure consistency, engagement, and credibility. They also emphasized that stable funding mechanisms are essential for the CoP’s long-term existence.

Sustainability charter

The Sustainability Charter must be developed to function as the project’s Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), providing the foundational direction for the entire Community of Practice (CoP). This Charter ensures the CoP actively “practices what it preaches” by requiring a holistic food systems approach to be implemented not only within the educational curriculum but also in the operational activities of all member institutions. By clearly defining these commitments, the Sustainability Charter provides the necessary framework for each university to subsequently develop their own sustainability roadmap. Finally, for the Sustainability Charter or similar frameworks, it was noted that clear guidelines and recommendations are needed to define what makes a university “sustainable” and how to assess progress.

Core member/Stakeholders

While universities were seen as a logical starting point, participants stressed that the core group should be more inclusive, involving representatives from different education levels and possibly public authorities or networks active in education for sustainability.

The core membership of the Community of Practice (CoP) should extend beyond traditional Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), which often operate as segregated entities. To break this “university bubble,” it should also

include Vocational Schools and Universities of Applied Sciences, which offer valuable examples of transdisciplinary learning and applied knowledge that bridge theory and practice.

There was also discussion around the sometimes-limited purpose-driven engagement of students in sustainability topics. Participants emphasized the need to actively involve students and create opportunities for their voices to shape the CoP’s direction and activities, ensuring that the community reflects the perspectives of future professionals and change agents.

Industry stakeholders are important but should act as external strategic partners rather than core decision-makers within the academic network.

Including the Ministries of Education of member states is vital for obtaining feedback on education policy and addressing country- or region-specific challenges.

Finally, the CoP should build on existing structures such as the ICA (Association for European Life Science Universities), which already connects to a broad university network. By functioning as a “network of networks,” the CoP can link regional ecosystems, maximize collective impact, and promote resource pooling toward shared goals.

Funding

The FutureFoodS Partnership could design specific calls for the CoP that align with the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA).

One option is to fund the establishment and operation of a university-based CoP, following the model of “university-driven food system ecosystems” adapted by the European Commission in the FoodPathS consortium. In this case, funding for the CoP’s organization could be sought through a dedicated call within the Partnership’s activities, improving alignment with its objectives and SRIA while ensuring coherent governance and strong links with the Observatory.

Alternatively, this approach could be integrated into a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) under FP10 as a distinct activity within a consortium of universities and Higher Education Institutions. The idea could also be explored in collaboration with EIT Food and other initiatives that promote networking in line with the sustainable food systems approach.

CoP connection to other domains

The CoP offers significant benefits to industry, particularly by addressing the persistent skill gaps in the current workforce. Industry actors could contribute by reviewing the mapping of Food Systems (FS) programmes to identify competency gaps and propose relevant updates to Ministries of Education.

These insights could form the basis for developing micro-credentials — short, targeted certifications that validate specific sustainability and food system skills, helping to rapidly close industry-identified competency gaps.

Beyond education, participants also saw potential in linking the CoP with other domains such as policy, innovation, and regional transitions, to foster cross-sector collaboration and ensure a more integrated approach to food system transformation.

From WP6 ‘RIPE’

WP6 specific recommendations are:

1. **Inclusive partnerships: urgent call to broaden participation.** All actors along the food system chain (not just a few) must be included.
2. **Design SMART SRIA topics that remain science-based but also acknowledge policy needs,** with a strong emphasis on interdisciplinarity and systems-oriented topics (the SRIA update process revealed a gap as many stakeholder inputs were policy or normative requests rather than researchable topics).
3. **Put the RIPE Concept as the organizing framework for the future Partnership,** integrating co-creation of SRIA with roadmap, best practice science-to-policy processes, alignment of food system education improvements, and integrated portfolio management across RIPE activities.
4. **A Food Systems Observatory (FSO) Should monitor transitions systemically,** showing relations between actors, activities, and outcomes:
 - a. Build on existing FS observatories but add transdisciplinary assessments.
 - b. Develop conceptual/statistical models showing interdependencies (e.g. diets, climate, safety).
 - c. Ensure governance that can consolidate reports on policy-relevant topics.
 - d. Include EU/national/local indicators, trade flows, investments, and private sector concentration.
 - e. Extend usability to civil society and food industry actors.

Since the RIPE concept has been extensively discussed during two workshops (one in Budapest, December 2024 and the other during the FOODPathS festival in Brussels May 2025), the RIPE concept has not been further discussed here in detail. Only the Policy elements are reported under WP3 ‘Funding’ due to a joint workshop during the FOODPathS annual meeting in The Hague, October 2025. The R&I part served already as basis for the SRIA. The Education part is now tackled by the Pact4Skills, and the preparatory Erasmus+ Agrifoodskills project. Still, an integrated, in-depth, action to connect the four RIPE pillars remains necessary in a future HE project.

Feedback from final meeting workshop session: Inclusive Science-to-Policy Dialogue

Please see the section From WP3 ‘Co-funding’, page 25.

From WP7 ‘Co-benefits and trade-offs’

WP7 specific recommendations are:

1. **Ensure inclusive and balanced governance** – Co-create a shared vision with all stakeholders, use clear communication, promote knowledge exchange, and balance power dynamics through fair access to advocacy, funding, and opportunities.
2. **Strengthen decision-making with diverse knowledge** – Ground discussions in reliable qualitative and quantitative data, ensure neutral facilitation, and value experimental and indigenous knowledge as complementary evidence.
3. **Align funding and research with real-world needs** – Involve broad stakeholder input, support place-based and adaptable initiatives, recognize diverse food system contexts, and foster interconnected networks across regions and supply chains.

These recommendations have been part of the discussions during the workshop on ‘working with the bird’ during the final FOODPathS meeting in The Hague. The main issues are described below under WP2 recommendations.

From WP8 'Communication, dissemination and exploitation'

WP8 specific recommendations are:

1. **Explanation of the key concepts to ensure a wider participation** - invest in explaining the key concepts (i.e., partnership, food systems, etc.) with a language that could be understood by every actor, including citizens, to support their engagement and involvement.
2. **Boost the collaboration opportunities** - collaboration is the most appreciated feature of a partnership according to stakeholders: in this sense, each partnership should ensure openness and transparency to ease the involvement of a wider range of actors and work for creating opportunities where they can meet, exchange and build new collaborations.

Since this WP8 is a transversal one, you will find the discussion on communication, dissemination and exploitation back in this entire Deliverable.

From WP2 'Co-creating the prototype P-SFS' (an integrative work package)

WP2 specific recommendations are:

Regarding governance:

1. A solid theoretical background for a conceptual governance framework has to be established for partnerships that are running for the long-term; this background serves for all actors involved as a reference and allows building trust.
2. Robust mapping of collaborative initiatives, using a single template to compare insights, is imperative to establish which governance issues are most relevant for divers' actors and contexts. Validation of practices via a sustainability impact study is needed in all cases.
3. A series of well-defined Mirror Group activities allow verifying trade-offs and co-benefits in time and in space.
4. Attention for and investing in new case studies remains fundamental to better understand co-benefits and trade-offs for the different kind of FS actors, and (local-global) citizens.
5. Developing a Code of Conduct enhances trust among partners, particularly in decision-making process, is a common request from divers' actors that needs to be taken seriously.
6. Involving an independent and impartial facilitator in the decision-making process is strongly recommended to avoid conflicts of interest and seek consensus.
7. Next to classical central roles of a governance board and executive committee, core bodies have to be revisited at the start and periodically updated; these are an Observatory, Knowledge Hub, Grouped Territorial Stakeholders Bodies (for broad FS actor involvement), a Funders Body, ...
8. The Funders Body is crucial in co-funded partnerships and have to be well positioned in the governance architecture.

Regarding agenda setting:

9. The most critical factor is the way a SRIA and action plan are formulated; the contribution and verification by the divers FS actors is considered imperative. The SRIA of a P-SFS, and preceding narrative, should be written and updated by representatives of different stakeholder groups in a language that is comprehensive for everyone. (WP2-6)
10. Without a sound science basis for food systems work, its R&I activities may become disperse and not well-evidenced based.
11. A cross analysis of SRIAs of related partnerships is recommended as a future activity.

12. Another strong recommendation is to further elaborate the RIPE concept via practical case studies and alignment with new Education & skills programs like e.g., proposed in the Pact4Skills. (WP2,3,4,5,6,7).

Regarding the *Modus Operandi*:

13. Clear definition of the *Modus Operandi* (MO) concept that is strongly linked to a partnership on Sustainable Food Systems activities e.g., by considering its funding constraints.
14. The impact in cultural dimensions in management should be taken into account; e.g., how cultural differences influence decision-making, communication, and collaboration.
15. The integration of digital tools and innovations in MO needs to be revisited and taken into account. E.g., AI-driven analytics and virtual collaboration tools could significantly enhance the operational efficiency and inclusivity of partnerships.
16. Conditions of scaling and adaptability have to be considered and further explored as well as cross-partnership collaboration (see chapter 8) to develop a community of practices for mutual learning.

Feedback from the final meeting session: ‘Working with the Bird’

‘How and where does the bird fly and land?’

Based on all recommendations given, and previous deliverables published, a workshop was organized to verify if one can work with the bird, and its key elements. This was held during the final project meeting in The Hague. The session was called ‘Working with the Bird’. Six groups were formed, all with a variety of food system actors. A set of scenarios – all targeting a kind of partnership – was proposed to the groups to check if the ‘bird methodology’ was practically applicable. The results of each group are presented below in a highly summarized way, with a short analysis paragraph at the end of this section.

Group 1: The chosen scenario has been “A university campus aiming to become more sustainable”. Their formulated mission was ‘Convince university management to adopt sustainable practices across all operations’. Regarding governance (head), the following active actors were proposed: students, teaching staff, university catering services, procurement office, principal’s office, external stakeholders (e.g., food councils, local municipality). With respect to the *modus operandi*, the following initial actions were prioritized: (i) organize a Hackathon event to bring different stakeholders together; (ii) develop an Action Plan as an early deliverable; and (iii) include sustainable practices into students’ daily life. The latter point targets ‘knowledge and experiences’ (the 2 wings), namely (a) integrate sustainable practices into teaching and learning. This requires the following infrastructure (tail): e.g., organize international summer schools, P2P learning exchanges, and new university gardens. Next, as observatory (eyes), a Sustainability Dashboard within the university is planned, showing Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), current status and progress and initial sustainability features and results. Finally, as a bird image, an eagle or duck is designed.

Group 2. The chosen scenario has been “Designing a governance and collaboration model for sustainable diets”. Their main discussion point was “If you don’t know where you are going, it is difficult to get there.” Regarding the governance structure (head), four key points have been noted: (i) nutritionists should play a leading role in governance; (ii) ministries and other institutions can support, but nutrition experts should guide direction; (iii) dietitians should contribute through experience-sharing and knowledge exchange; and (iv) who should play a leading role really depends on each one’s perception connected to their role in the food systems. Before elaborating the other elements of the bird, 2 key questions/reflections to implement the bird are: (1) “Who is designing the bird? Who is included? Who is using the model?” and (2) “Where is the bird going or landing? If you don’t know that it is hard to develop a model”. The time was lacking to further reflect on the bird’s elements. The model developed by Group 2 is represented as a KIWI bird, without wings and tail.

Group 3. The chosen scenario was “Creating a partnership of partnerships”. Their governance (head) consists of an Executive Board and Council to ensure strategic alignment between partnerships and ethical oversight. A *modus operandi* (body) was considered for the partnership coordinators responsible for daily operations and regular meetings (both online and in-person). The knowledge and experiences (wings) as well as the infrastructure (tail) focuses on the alignment of the different SRIAs and learnings from best practices. Finally, the observatory (eyes) served for transparent sharing of information and continuous feedback loops.

Group 4. The chosen scenario has been “Collaboration among European regions with shared needs and goals”. For governance (head), the main outcome was to align governance models across regions to ensure coherent and flexible decision-making. Synchronized decisions with regional initiatives and secured political support were considered crucial. Government actors share best practices and enthusiasm for innovation. For experience & knowledge (wings) co-creation cases at local level are considered most relevant. They connect to regional platforms, enabling specialization and reveal complementarity among regions. Technical expertise and knowledge transfer support the platforms. Regarding the *modus operandi* (body), the focus is on training programs, mobilization of core and new funding sources. Finally, as infrastructure (tail), most relevant is a Knowledge Hub to store and disseminate insights.

Group 5. The chosen scenario has been “Developing and scaling systems for alternative protein production”. Governance (head) unites farmers, consumers, and local governments. For experience & knowledge (wings), the major points are to ensure safe production, consumer protection, and data analysis as well as to map good practices and failures to inform future interventions. With respect to the *modus operandi* (body), operational structures ensures that ecosystems around alternative proteins are financially feasible. Finally, the infrastructure (tail) provides methodologies for designing and implementing effective strategies.

Group 6. The chosen scenario has been “Creating a partnership of partnerships”. For governance (head), working groups are composed of representatives from different work packages to explore synergies. Their goal is to create a rotating secretariat to ensure shared leadership and responsibility. The observatory (eyes) serves to monitor how existing partnerships and observatories operate, assess their indicators, and identify improvements. Their approach is to start from objectives, and include both qualitative and quantitative data to build narratives. The *modus operandi* (body) delivers joint funding initiatives, stakeholder incentives (e.g., regulatory changes), strong communication strategies, and focus on behavioral change. The model developed by Group 2 is represented as a Frankenstein bird.

A discussion and analysis of the bird methodology provided some interesting statements of participants to the following three questions:

I. Which elements of the bird were most difficult to understand and apply?

- “The head (governance) and tail (infrastructure) were the most challenging elements. They require balancing power relations, ensuring inclusivity, and building trust across diverse stakeholders. These structures also depend on long-term funding and sustained commitment”.
- “I think it was quite easy to understand all of the elements. Most discussion we had was about the “left” and “right” wings, and perhaps they also bring into mind some political connotations. We also discussed the connection between the observatory i.e. the eyes, vs. the brain. But eventually, in my opinion, their respective roles were clear”.

II. Which elements of the bird were easiest to understand and discuss?

- “I guess the wings (knowledge and experience) were the most intuitive components. Stakeholders easily relate to exchanging knowledge, learning from case studies, and building capacity. The nerve system (communication and dissemination) was also easy to discuss”.
- “The role of the body, and basic functions, was easy to understand”.

III. What guidance would help you most to apply the model to another scenario?

- “Simplify abstract components (e.g., governance, observatory) into practical guiding questions: Who makes decisions? How do we learn? What data help us steer?”
- “I think head, eyes, and tail require deeper systemic understanding and coordination, but wings, body, and nerve system offer concrete starting points for dialogue, cooperation, and collective action. Maybe some more examples, and to clarify the role of the wings.”

Overall, it became apparent that 5 of the 6 groups were able to use the bird concept for a very rapid description of their chosen ‘partnership’. The sixth group didn’t have the time to elaborate the bird-partnership but poses several questions that may be relevant for anybody developing a partnership.

5. Recommendations from single partners representing a network

Since FOODPathS partners represent a variety of networks from local to global scales – and with different legal status – here, a series of recommendations is presented that originate from them. These recommendations have been fueled by the 3.5 years of work done in FOODPathS by partners and their networks.

A future look by ICLEI ‘Local-to-Global Food Systems: Connecting Cities, Regions, and the World’

Urbanization is reshaping food systems worldwide, bringing both opportunities and challenges, and introducing complex trade-offs with social, nutritional, and environmental implications. The expansion of urban and peri-urban areas influences how territories and regions are organized and how people produce, access and consume food. Today, over half of the world’s population lives in urban and peri-urban areas, which together account for more than 70% of global food consumption—a not insignificant amount of which is wasted. These areas also face alarming levels of food insecurity, with around 75% of communities experiencing moderate to severe food shortages¹. At the same time, malnutrition in all its forms—including undernutrition, micronutrient deficiencies, overweight, and obesity—is rising, reflecting rapid dietary transitions, growing inequalities, and fragmented governance in urban food systems. Understanding the local and global dimensions of these trends is critical for designing and implementing sustainable, equitable, and resilient food systems that can meet the needs of our growing population.

In the FOODPathS project, we engaged local, regional, European, and global partners actively working on sustainable food systems². Through these interactions, we learned that transforming Europe’s food system demands a fundamental shift from post-war, production-driven models towards approaches that are sustainable, equitable, and resilient. Decades of investment in industrial agriculture and centralized power among large processors and retailers has created structural lock-ins, limiting flexibility for change. Addressing these challenges requires redistributing power, fostering accountability, and embracing systemic, context-specific solutions that span the entire supply chain. Key gaps persist—unequal access to food, weak policy coherence, insufficient funding, and limited trust and communication between actors across the food system. Moving forward, transformation must balance technological and social innovation, strengthen local capacities, and connect local action to global responsibility to build food systems that are healthy, fair, and sustainable for all.

Initiatives like the MUFPP (around Milan) and ICLEI CityFood³ demonstrate how local action can drive global transformation by unlocking the potential of multi-level food governance—connecting governments vertically across scales and horizontally across sectors and stakeholders. Through CityFood’s *Triple H Approach*—Healthy People, Healthy Climate, Healthy Landscape—the programme supports cities and regions in designing locally relevant, systemic solutions that address health, environmental, and social challenges in an integrated way. By fostering collaboration, innovation, and shared responsibility, this approach turns local initiatives into catalysts for broader, global change toward sustainable and resilient food systems.

Building sustainable food systems from local to global levels demands smart, coordinated investment. Cities and regions need support to strengthen local food governance, improve and adapt infrastructure, and encourage circular, low-carbon models that reduce waste and emissions. Investment is equally vital for innovation, education, and collaboration—empowering local actors to turn good ideas into lasting impact. By investing in Healthy People, Healthy Climate, and Healthy Landscapes, we invest in a future where every city nourishes both people and the planet.

¹ High Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition (HLPE). (2024). Strengthening urban and peri-urban food systems to achieve food security and nutrition, in the context of urbanization and rural transformation. Rome, CFS HLPE-FSN.

² reference D7.1 : <https://www.foodpaths.eu/in-action/partnership-inclusivity/> and <https://www.foodpaths.eu/in-action/partnership-inclusivity/>

³ <https://cityfood-program.org/our-approach>

A future look by SEAMK- ERIAFF ‘a robust monitoring and evaluation system’

A follow-up project, relevant for regions and others, could focus on developing a robust monitoring and evaluation system for sustainable food systems. Building on the most impactful pilots – regenerative farming and circular economy practices, short food chains with digital platforms, and consumer/restaurant pilots – regional hubs would serve as testbeds for collecting and analyzing data.

Key indicators would include carbon footprint, food waste, employment effects, and also social aspects such as community well-being and education outcomes, benchmarked against regional and national goals.

By documenting and scaling best practices, and engaging stakeholders through training, communication and policy dialogue, the project aims to deliver evidence-based models that support long-term integration of monitoring frameworks into sustainable food system policies.

A future look by Confagricoltura and FoodDrinkEurope, with the support of Federalimentare and the NFTPs: ‘Institutionalized Public-Private Partnership for the European Agrifood Sector: Strategy and Governance’

Introduction

The transition towards sustainable agrifood systems is a strategic priority for the European Union. Achieving this requires coordinated action from public authorities, research institutions, and private actors, supported by effective governance. The creation of an Institutionalized Public-Private Partnership (PPP) for the European agrifood sector represents a strategic opportunity to accelerate investment in sustainability and innovation while strengthening Europe’s position in the global agrifood competitive economy. This chapter focuses on three interconnected aspects: (i) the importance of private sector engagement at different levels, (ii) designing an inclusive governance framework, and (iii) key recommendations and strategic actions of a new Food4All Partnership.

The Role of the Private Sector and Levels of Engagement

Private sector involvement is crucial for building resilient and competitive agrifood systems. With SMEs representing most of the food industry (95% of the 290.000 Eu companies) and more than approximately 9.1 million farms in the EU (Eurostat, 2020) contributing to 21.5 million employees and a turnover of the agrifood chain estimated at approximately €3.6–3.7 trillion (FoodDrinkEurope/Eurostat, 2023–2024), the agrifood industry is a cornerstone of the EU economy. However, the perception that SMEs are slow innovators is misleading. While fewer firms invest in breakthrough research, incremental innovation remains widespread and crucial for long-term transformation.

These mid-sized enterprises (mid-caps in the Draghi Report), together with SMEs, drive bottom-up innovation through agility and territorial rootedness, acting as multipliers by demonstrating successful innovations and fostering peer-to-peer learning, thereby reducing adoption costs across the value chain. Philanthropic organizations and civil society actors further support this process by bridging EU strategic objectives with local implementation, promoting education and the dissemination of sustainable practices in remote or peripheral areas. By leveraging existing EU and national networks, innovation can remain both territorially grounded and aligned with broader EU sustainability goals. In this context, two operational principles are essential:

- **Granularity:** selecting the right tool to address specific problems and maximize innovation pillars.
- **Capillarity:** ensuring appropriate interventions reach all actors at different geographical levels of the European agrifood ecosystem.

These principles guarantee that innovation is both scalable and inclusive, preventing concentration and supporting territorial diversity in a long-term framework. Building long-term, trust-based Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) is essential for strengthening Europe's R&D&I ecosystem. The PPP framework enables engagement at multiple levels, from large multinational corporations, which provide scale, investment capacity, and global reach, to direct participation in collaborative research and the scaling of innovations through Mid Cap Champions.

Designing an Inclusive Governance Framework for the Partnership

Co-funded Partnerships, such as FutureFoodS, already operate within governance models primarily defined by funding bodies and academic partners. However, the private sector has often been underrepresented in these structures. Regulation (EU) 2021/2085 provides flexibility in governance (Regulation establishing Joint Undertakings under Horizon Europe) while requiring equal representation of EU institutions and private stakeholders. The proposed Governance model is a preliminary, multi-layered structure designed to balance inclusiveness with operational efficiency:

- **General Assembly:** sets strategic orientation and represents a broad spectrum of agrifood actors, including national trade organizations, technology platforms, SMEs, large companies, and civil society.
- **Board of Directors:** deliberative body of 14–15 members, equally shared between the European Commission and private sector representatives.
- **Executive Director:** leads operational implementation of strategic decisions.
- **Technical-Scientific Committee:** guides research agenda and ensures evidence-based recommendations.
- **Regional/Territorial Advisory Group:** integrates local and regional perspectives and territorial diversity into governance.
- **Conciliation and Arbitration Board:** guarantees conflict resolution and trust-building.

Governance arrangements must reflect the territorial and economic diversity of stakeholders' networks and intermediary organizations, which regulate and represent the composite nature of the Agrifood economy. One potential answer could be a dual-affiliation governance system – from farmers and companies to Regional and National Associations and from Associations to EU umbrella organizations and coordinated Networks - ensuring that private-sector representation reflects the leading role of the European agri-food industry while preserving balanced decision-making.

Key recommendations and strategic actions of the Food4All Partnership

The current political and economic context requires flexible and adaptive policies in the EU agrifood sector. Food security, food safety, risk management, sustainability, and long-term resilience are interconnected priorities that require careful balance and must be addressed through tailored approaches. National agrifood systems in Europe are highly diverse in terms of company size, territorial characteristics, crop and livestock profiles, supply chain structures, and access to technological and scientific support. Consequently, a one-size-fits-all strategy would be ineffective and potentially risky. Policies should instead embrace flexibility, granularity, and bottom-up approaches, enabling interventions that respond to local conditions and capacities. By investing in innovation-ready firms of appropriate size and ensuring that knowledge flows through dense inter-firm networks, Europe can accelerate systemic change across the agrifood value chain.

A practical example of this approach is the new but ambivalent concept of “re-nationalization” within a harmonized EU framework, as reflected in the revised Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). This allows countries and regions to implement tailored measures that promote sustainability, stimulate innovation, and facilitate risk sharing, supported by targeted financial and regulatory tools while remaining aligned with broader European objectives. Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) play a central role to accelerate innovation, facilitate market uptake, and enable industrial and commercial scaling. The concept of partnership we favor aims at reducing fragmentation and avoiding duplication of research efforts, while simultaneously increasing private investment in R&I activities.

The strategy prioritizes investment in innovative SMEs, leveraging their agility and diversity to generate improvements across the agrifood system and trigger network effects that inspire wider adoption. Mid Cap Champions reinforce this dynamic by showcasing the benefits of new technologies, fostering peer learning, and

building collaborative networks. As innovations spread, costs fall, adoption increases, and systemic change accelerates, benefiting the entire agrifood value chain. By drawing on the food industry’s extensive expertise across the entire value chain—from production to distribution and retailing — the private sector emerges not only as a driver of innovation but also as a central actor in promoting sustainable practices and connecting directly with consumers to encourage responsible food choices.

The private sector should be understood not as a standalone entity but as a core component of public-private partnerships, where collaboration makes it possible to combine complementary resources, generate synergies, and stimulate stronger innovation. The NFTP illustrates a clear example of this model effectively. Key stakeholders—such as Agrifood Associations/Federations and Confederations and European Technology Platforms (ETPs and NFTPs)—play a central role by leveraging their extensive networks of experts and sector-specific knowledge to drive innovation and collaboration across the sector. NFTPs have historically driven in other sectors the establishment of high-profile PPPs under previous research and innovation frameworks. Workforce development is another critical pillar of the innovation strategy. Aligned with the European Pact4Skills initiative and the 2030-2040-2050 scenarios (FORUM 2050), targeted programs facilitate the transfer of skills from research to practical applications, with local communities playing a vital role in promoting adoption. By fostering upskilling and reskilling through collaboration among academic institutions, educational agencies, companies, private VET providers and social partners (Entrepreneurs and Unions), the sector is prepared for future innovation pathways and emerging technological challenges.

Conclusion

By 2040, EU agrifood systems should be globally competitive, aligned with UN SDGs and the EU reviewed Green Deal, and capable of ensuring food security under stringent sustainability standards. The success of the Food4All Partnership depends on a strong agriculture-industry-consumer alliance, which can bridge gaps in investment and strategy, particularly in less-developed regions, while promoting education, awareness, collaboration between public and private entities, and bottom-up innovation. This alliance, guided by the principles of granularity and capillarity in a dual affiliation system, ensures that local ecosystems of SMEs and farmers are fully engaged and that innovations diffuse throughout the supply chain, reaching even peripheral regions and smaller producers. The Food4All Institutionalized Partnership provides a platform for mobilizing public and private resources, foster innovation, and ensure inclusive and effective governance. With the active engagement from all actors, it offers a blueprint for achieving the EU’s long-term objectives, positioning European agrifood systems as global leaders in sustainability, resilience, skilling and competitiveness.

Notes and References

- Regulation (EU) 2021/2085 establishing Joint Undertakings under Horizon Europe: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32021R2085>
- Eurostat (2020 Farm Structure Survey): ~9.1 million farms. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/>
- FoodDrinkEurope (2023): Food and drink industry turnover ~€1.1–1.4 trillion; full food chain ~€3.6–3.7 trillion. <https://www.fooddrinkeurope.eu/>
- WUR and other modelling studies on food system transition: reductions in GHG up to ~70%, land use ~40–60%. <https://www.wur.nl/en.htm>

A future look by CORE Organic Network and the International Centre for Research in Organic Food Systems (AU-ICROFS)

The CORE Organic (CO) network has supported European organic food and farming R&I efforts since 2004. In response to growing organic sector needs, initially the network was launched under the ERA-Net transnational funding and cooperation scheme. Over four programme periods the ERA-Net CORE Organic partners funded [62 research projects](#) for 61.9 million EUR. Presently, the network operates under the [OrganicTargets4EU](#) project (2022-2026) and it encompasses 43 partners from 28 countries/regions in the EU and beyond.

The main objective of the network is to ensure policy support in research areas relevant for the organic sector, particularly to support the implementation of the **European Farm to Fork Strategy (2020)** with the target of at least 25% of EU agricultural land to be under organic farming by 2030 and continuous growth of the sector including aquaculture, aiming to create a sustainable, healthy and environmentally friendly food system [EUR-Lex - 52020DC0381 - EN - EUR-Lex](#) . To achieve this target and help the organic sector to reach its full potential the Commission has put forward the **EU Organic Action Plan (2021-2027)**, which sets the aim to dedicate at least 30% of the budget in Intervention Area 3 “Agriculture, forestry and rural areas” of Cluster 6 of Horizon Europe to topics specific to or relevant for the organic sector. The EU Organic Action Plan also aims to strengthen coordination of national organic food R&I programmes via the Horizon Europe mission, A Soil Deal for Europe, and via the partnerships on Agroecology, FutureFoodS, and Animal Health and Welfare [EUR-Lex - 52021DC0141R\(01\) - EN - EUR-Lex](#) .

ICROFS as the CORE Organic network Programme Secretariat has conducted an impact assessment study with the relevant HEU Partnerships, Partnership AGROECOLOGY and FutureFoodS, and CSA Green ERA Hub, covering the period from early 2024 and focusing on organic R&I opportunities in the current framework programme. Based on the preliminary results of the analysis of publicly available information such as the Partnership SRIAs, call texts, evaluation procedures, and selected projects, study has indicated a risk that research for development of organic food and farming may be overlooked in the overarching broad themes of the partnerships/ missions/ other relevant funding instruments.

Recommendations for HEU funding schemes for reaching at least 30% of the funding for organics is to focus on all aspects of research programme and transnational call life cycle:

- 1. Development of the SRIA:** Make stakeholder consultation with the European Commission DG Agri, Organic Unit and stakeholder umbrella organization TP Organics to ensure that the Partnership or other programme SRIAs contain the subjects most relevant for the organic sector. Include specific information on objectives in relation to development of organic food and farming to reach the goal of 25% organic area in the EU in 2030.
- 2. Call text:** Include more specific references to organic targets in the call text, and which challenges in organic production the proposals need to address. Include a ticking box in the proposal template for indication if the R&I proposal is ‘specific to’, or ‘relevant for’ the organic sector. Negotiate possibilities to set aside a certain percentage of the budget for research ‘specific to’ or ‘relevant for’ organic food and farming.
- 3. Selection of experts:** If the project is ‘specific for organic food and farming’ at least two of the experts should have documented knowledge on organic food and farming, and if the project is ‘relevant for organic production’ at least one of the experts should have relevant documented expertise within organic food and farming.
- 4. Evaluation procedure:** Include relevant criteria in the proposal evaluation material for project relevance and impact on organic food and farming.
- 5. Selection/ monitoring of projects:** Include estimates of the budget going to research ‘specific to’ or ‘relevant

for' organic food and farming in the selection procedure to ensure that the 30% funding of research 'specific to' or 'relevant for' organic food and farming will be reached by the calls. Develop relevant project criteria and impact indicators to be used during the project monitoring.

6. **Evaluation of research programmes/ calls funded by Partnerships/ Missions/ relevant funding instruments (e.g., CSA Green ERA Hub):** Define indicators for evaluation of the funding programme as regards the impact on organic food and farming development and innovation. Compile a list of R&I projects specific, respectively relevant for organic food and farming, and estimate the percentage of total call/ programme funding spent on the organic sector compared to the total spending on funded R&I projects. Make procedures for how to reach the ambition of the EU Commission to reach at least 30% of total funding in Cluster 6, Area 3 on organic food and farming.

Recommendations to the European Commission as regards how to ensure that the ambition of minimum 30 % research funding in Cluster 6/ Area 3 contributes to development of organic food and farming.

7. **Define criteria** for projects 'specific to' or 'relevant for' the organic sector to be used in the Horizon Europe instruments.
8. **Collect data** from relevant partnerships, missions and other relevant funding instruments on how much of their funding budget has been dedicated to research 'specific to' or 'relevant for' organic food and farming systems compared to their total project funding.
9. **Coordinate with relevant Partnerships/ Missions/ other relevant funding instruments on how to reach the ambition of 30% funding to organic food and farming** and how to document that this ambition has been reached.
10. **Secure funding in Horizon Europe calls** for projects specific to the organic sector that covers objectives of more than one Partnership.
11. **Evaluate on the project level how much of the total funding in Cluster 6, Area 3 of Horizon Europe calls is dedicated to research 'specific to' or 'relevant for' development of the organic sector** and benchmark with total project funding.
12. **Evaluate on the research programme level the impact of available funding in Cluster 6, Area 3 as regards to development of the organic sector Farm to Fork 25% goal for the organic area in 2030, and the minimum 30% of the HEU funding budget for Cluster 6, Area 3 set aside for organic food and farming R&I.**

A future look by INRAE and its experiences in the OnePlanetNetwork on ‘Governing Trade-offs in multi-level and multi-actor partnerships’

The following recommendations also aim to contribute to the development of the FutureFoodS Partnership. These recommendations are based on the experiences of twenty-seven existing multi-actor and multi-level initiatives. We examined how these initiatives negotiate decision-making, and manage trade-offs inherent to sustainability transitions. Sustainable food system initiatives operate across multiple governance scales and decision levels, facing tensions between institutionalization and flexibility, inclusion and targeting, and more broadly on how trade-offs are conceived: do they inevitably create ‘winners and losers,’ or can they be structured to benefit more stakeholders?

Key insights and Recommendations

1. Promote adaptive governance across scales and levels to strengthen coherence

Coherent food system’ governance requires connecting multiple scales and decision levels – including a wide variety of stakeholders - while managing sustainability trade-offs. The key trade-off highlighted across the 27 studied initiatives comes from the tension between keeping global frameworks of sustainable transition consistent and adapting them to local needs. This calls for “level-shifting” strategies aligning the institutional scales and the constitutional, collective, and operational decisions. To provide an example, the Agroecology Hubs implemented by Biovision facilitate level-shifting by linking local initiatives into regional networks which are further linked to international working groups. It is in this way that they achieved to integrate the concept of Agroecology in a wide array of policy interventions concerning various parts of the food system, including agricultural production, natural resource management, education, research and extension, value chain development, markets, public procurement, consumption and food safety.

2. Reframe inclusion as empowerment, not mere representation

Another key finding is that inclusion alone does not guarantee meaningful influence; various initiatives show that participatory structures must be paired with empowerment measures—such as co-decision and capacity building—to enhance legitimacy, equity, and in the end inclusive decision-making spaces. For instance, GAIN uses co-creation tools, such as Participatory Mapping and a Photo Voice tool, that enable participants to produce their own storytelling and to situate it within the broader global food landscape. Moreover, these tools create spaces where stakeholders can validate, adjust, and enrich knowledge, rather than merely serving as objects of data collection. In this sense, they also help ensure transparency within the governance structures of their organization.

3. Use trade-offs as strategic levers for transition

Eventually, trade-offs are structural moments where values and power relations are negotiated. They should be treated as productive dynamics rather than obstacles and moments to avoid. Our research shows that while intentional choices and trade-offs across social, environmental, and economic aspects explain the goals of governance arrangements: it describes their objectives, but not the dynamics that concretely shape governance processes. Reframing trade-offs – especially *process trade-offs* that are involved in rule implementation, scale management, and actor coordination - can serve as strategic and analytical ways to better understand and improve governance. This approach shows that “good governance” principles aren’t universal rules, but tools that people use differently depending on the context. For example, some initiatives may prioritize representativity, while others emphasize empowerment, transparency, or knowledge translation across stakeholders. By making these trade-offs explicit and constructive, initiatives can better navigate heterogeneous coalitions and design governance arrangements that are adapted to the context and inclusivity in the process.

To sum-up, sustainable transition of food systems depends on negotiating, adapting, and contextualizing trade-offs rather than standardizing models that should be scaled up. Linking governance scales, empowering meaningful inclusion, managing trade-offs constructively, and fostering knowledge co-production enhances legitimacy, efficiency, and transformative potential in sustainable food systems.

6. Deliverables and publications for further reading

See: <https://zenodo.org/communities/foodpaths/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Deliverable no.	Deliverable name
D1.1	Evaluation of management tools and procedures
D2.1	Report of mapping results
D2.2	Report of FS approaches and Observatory
D2.3	Manual of Prototype Partnership 1.0
D2.4	Functioning FS Approaches & Observatory
D2.5	Modus operandi protocol
D2.6	Innovative governance model
D2.7	Manual & Presentation of the Prototype 2.0 Partnership SSFS
D2.8	Summary of Partnership guidance/mentoring activities presented
D3.1	Report on funders engagement and forum agenda
D3.2	Aligned network and strategies for co-funding
D4.1	Examples of private-public collaborations for a SFS partnership
D4.2	European Central Hub of FS Labs
D5.1	Report with assessed skills and knowledge gaps
D5.2	Branded Network of exemplary university-driven ecosystems, sustainability charter
D6.1	SRIA2.0 & Guidelines for science-policy interface
D6.2	RIPE concept (SRIA3.0, S-to-P, Education) with Food2030 co-benefits, incl SSH & digitalization
D7.1	Report on trade-offs and co-benefits
D7.2	Toolkit for co-benefits & trade-offs with liaised (international/local) actors
D8.1	Plan for C&D&E activities
D8.2	Data Management Plan
D8.3	Feedback from society
D8.4	Prototype 2.0 Partnership SSFS 'launch festival'
Scientific papers on:	Co-creation, governance, intermediaries, business models for SFS, methodology for studying FS, food science for P-SFS

Annex 1. Agendas from the workshops held during the annual FOODPathS meeting in The Hague, October 2025

Workshop Session ‘Working with the Bird’

The agenda of the session:

- Introduction and welcomes, introduction to the bird w/example
- Introduction to the exercise, addressing -multi-actor approach -co-creation -interdisciplinarity
- Working in small groups on the Bird Puzzle:
 - Assign a facilitator and note taker
 - Small groups apply the bird model to their assigned/chosen scenario or to create very rapidly their own scenario: Group participants will work collaboratively (or in pairs) on each “bird piece” to develop it based on the chosen scenario. **Example:** For the “Head” puzzle piece, the group will define a governance structure suitable for addressing their selected scenario. Notes can be written directly on the puzzle piece.
 - Address the question ‘what type of bird are you building? A hawk?’
 - Use the Bird puzzle pieces with prompts on the backside. There are also ‘Small’ hands out of the bird · 5 minutes to get into groups, 5 minutes to come back together
- Introducing the flock of birds by giving the floor to 1 person per group to provide their bird.

Regarding the constitution of the group and Duration, it is recommended to have representatives of different food system actor groups involved. The duration of the exercise is arbitrary. A first image of the bird model can be created in 1 hour; however, a more detailed description asks for at least a half a day.

An example of a scenario to create your unique bird model: “Urban-rural strategy to fight food insecurity”. Apply the bird model for a partnership that develops an urban-rural food systems strategy to counteract food insecurity for all its inhabitants. For example, the city council and philanthropic foundations may be in the lead, but all other kind of food systems actors are actively involved, supported by the citizens.

Workshop session ‘Science-to-policy & R&I programming (funding)’

The session gathered representatives from European and national administrations, research organizations, funding agencies, regional innovation networks, and stakeholder platforms to discuss how science–policy interfaces (SPI/SPSI) and research and innovation (R&I) programming can best support the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the future Sustainable Food Systems Partnership.

The session was divided into two complementary parts:

- Part I explored how research-based advice is used by policy makers and how science–policy interfaces can be organized to ensure dialogue, inclusiveness, and integrity.
- Part II examined how policy needs can inform R&I programming and project design, focusing on sectoral coordination, funding-cycle continuity, and mechanisms for embedding policy relevance within projects themselves.

Workshop session 'Knowledge Hub & Communities of Practice'

The ambitions of the sessions are presented in the following 2 images.

Let's co-create!

- Please use the color note that correspond to your stakeholder group (policymaker, industry, researcher)

Discussion question

- 1) Define the domain of the CoP
- 2) What can CoP offer to the community and how the community offer to CoP
- 3) How to attract core member to the CoP

Aim of this session

- Identify the priority functionalities and services that the Knowledge Hub should provide.
- Explore possible governance and sustainability models to ensure the Hub is long-lasting and inclusive.
- Define the next concrete steps towards the full deployment of the Knowledge Hub

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